

**INDIGENOUS AND CONTEMPORARY FOODS CONSUMPTION
AMONG ADOLESCENTS AND OLD PEOPLE IN
AKOKO NORTH WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT
AREA OF ONDO STATE**

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Abstract

The study examined the consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods among adolescents and elders in Akoko North West Local Government Area (ANWLGA) of Ondo State. The study was carried out on one hundred and ninety-two adolescents and elders in ANWLGA of Ondo State. Thirty-two (elders and adolescents) were purposively selected in six randomly selected wards. A questionnaire subjected to face and content validation and was administered on the elders and adolescents in the local government area. Four research questions and three hypotheses were stated to guide the findings of the study. Responses from the questionnaire were analysed descriptively and inferentially using frequency counts, simple percentage, mean and t-test. Major findings revealed that more adolescents consumed contemporary foods than elders while elders consumed indigenous foods than the adolescents. The indigenous foods consumed by the elders were esurú, arirú, àbàrí, iyán, kókò, sèsé, ègbo, àádùn, òjòjò, egidi, èkuru and àkàrá ágbádo. Findings also revealed that there was a significant difference in the perception of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods and that there was a significant difference in the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State. It was recommended that the indigenous foods, most especially the ones that are not often consumed by adolescents should be encouraged through traditional kitchens, television broadcast, publication of recipes in magazines and dailies and that education, promotion and social marketing to expose the importance of indigenous foods should be targeted to key age groups such as children, adolescents and youths.

Keywords: Indigenous foods, contemporary foods, adolescents, elders.

Introduction

Food is as important as human existence and for any individual to stay alive and healthy, such an individual is expected to eat. According to Maslow Hierarchy of needs, man cannot survive without having access to the physiological needs such as housing, clothing, food and water. These basic needs are fundamentally required for the continual growth and development of human species. The benefits of indigenous foods in the rural communities cannot be overemphasized. The fact that food is often cheap and affordable to the small scale resource, poor rural dwellers and the nutritional benefits it offers. Indigenous food crops refer to crops that have their origin in a particular country or locality (Fasakin, 2018). Added to these crops are those that were introduced into the country and are now recognised as naturalised or traditional crops. These crops are produced and found growing in the country under various weather conditions with many found in the wild. Indigenous food crops could be grains, vegetables and fruits.

Traditional or indigenous food sources may be plants or animals that are consumed by indigenous people. In Nigeria, several plants traditionally consumed have good nutritive value. Edible parts may be young leaves or stems, flowers and fruits, and may be eaten fresh, cooked as side dishes or garnishment. For instance, some of the indigenous foods in Akoko are *esuru*, *aruru*, *abari*, pounded yam, cocoyam, *sese* which are produced when foodstuffs used are in season. These plants may be from the farms or home gardens which are natural sources. Indigenous and traditional foods, if promoted among the younger generations of the rural dwellers could help to solve the global problem of poverty, hunger and malnutrition (Faber and Wenhold, 2007). In the rural communities of most of the developing countries (Nigeria inclusive) access to balance nutrition is gradually becoming a challenge as the influence of

contemporary or foreign foodstuffs such as polished rice, noodles and other western foods have almost suppressed the consumption of indigenous foods which play important role in the lives of children and adult population.

There is no particular definition for contemporary foods. However, in this study, contemporary foods will be regarded as foods evolving as a result of post-colonial activities and not being native to a particular country or region. It also involves fast foods, snacks and junk foods of the century. Prior to the advent of contemporary and western foods, households live essentially on natural foods cultivated and processed using traditional and indigenous methods. Even the condiments used in cooking were sourced locally from indigenous plants materials. For examples, *Iru* (dadawa or locust bean) and shea-butter are being replaced with "maggi cubes" and the likes. Examples of indigenous foods in the Western Nigeria among others are *ekuru*, *abari*, *egbo*, *sako*, *aadun*, *aje-pass*, *ojojo*, *sagidi* which serve as snacks or main meals in households. Invariably, these foods are gradually fading off and been replaced by the modern foods or snacks which may not even compare with the later in terms of nutritional benefits or value and affordability. However, it is important to note that what people eat or consume is influenced by social factors, cultural practices and their ability to purchase the food items.

According to Faber and Wenhold (2007), a decline in the use of indigenous foods results in nutritional deficiency especially among rural households. For example, In Nigeria, rice production is in the hands of small scale farmers who use traditional methods and lack the capacity to add value to what they produce. This situation could frustrate farmers to diversify production, reduce stocking to minimize losses and adopt other measures that are capable of undermining their initial production plan (Adefalu, Usman, Omotesho, Aderinoye-

Abdulwahab & Olateju, 2013). This scenario is occasioned by the migration of the urban and rural people from local rice consumption which is often poorly finished to the imported polished rice.

Dietary intake of traditional leafy vegetables has been reported to have healing properties and serve as a source of micronutrients (Flyman & Afolayan, 2006; Frison, 2007). This reduces the risk of cardiovascular diseases and other degenerative diseases (Smith & Eyzaguirre, 2007). As in the case of this study, indigenous foods include traditional leafy vegetables and traditional foods that are either native to a particular region, or were introduced to that region for a long period to evolve through natural processes or farmer selection, including both wild and traditionally cultivated vegetables or foods by the natives in a region. Previous studies have shown that indigenous or traditional foods adapt well to harsh environments, are easy to grow, require simpler technology and low inputs (Van der Walt, Mossanda, Jivan, Swart & Bezuidenhout, 2005) and have the ability to resist pathogens, thus requiring fewer chemicals and pesticides (Abukutsa-Onyango, 2007). Despite the self-reported contributions of indigenous foods to health, nutrition and food security at household level, several studies reported that the production and consumption of indigenous foods have declined (Mbhenyane, Venter, Vorster & Steyn, 2005; Faber, van Jaarsveld & Laubscher, 2007).

A study by Fasakin (2018) in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State revealed that the indigenous foods in the area includes, *àmúyalé* or *àmúyagi*, *obe ifun*, *gbanunu*, *letti*, *eepa*, *tapon*, *eepo logun* and *ekuu ogede*, but were not consumed frequently. Fasakin's study has provided evidence for the poor consumption of indigenous food items. However, the present study examined the consumption of indigenous food relative to contemporary food and the difference by age.

Statement

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Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, poverty, poor nutrition and hunger are increasingly becoming a challenge which successive government administrations have not been able to tackle. This is so because the population of the people particularly those in the rural areas where the purchasing power is very low is increasing astronomically while agricultural productivity which is presumed to provide employment and eliminate hunger and poverty is decreasing arithmetically. The increasing rate at which people abandon indigenous and traditional food in the rural communities spells doom for a nation whose population is predominantly rural based. The problem of hunger and malnutrition in the rural communities is not only associated with the non-availability of food but that of failure to leverage on the advantages indigenous food processing procedures offer. As a way of making food available to households, it becomes imperative that people begin to look inward for the consumption of more indigenous and traditionally processed food. In the light of the problems enumerated above, this study therefore examined the consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods among adolescents and elders in Akoko North West Local Government Area (ANWLGA) of Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the findings of the study

1. What are the indigenous and contemporary foods consumed by adolescents and the elderly in ANWLGA, Ondo State?
2. What is the perception of adolescents and elderly on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State?
3. What are the reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and the elderly in ANWLGA, Ondo State?

4. What is the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and the elderly in ANWLGA, Ondo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the perception of adolescents and elderly on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elderly in ANWLGA, Ondo State

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elderly in ANWLGA, Ondo State.

Methodology

Design

The design used for the study was descriptive survey. This design was adopted because descriptive studies make no attempt to manipulate variables, and it is concerned with describing and interpreting existing relationships, attitudes practical processes and tends to compare variables (Isaac, 2002).

Sample and Sampling Technique

For the purpose of this study, simple random and purposive sampling techniques were used. Six (6) wards were selected from the ten wards by balloting. The wards selected were Arigidi II, Arigidi/Iye I, Erusu, Esc/Afin, Ogbagi and Oyin/Oge. Purposive sampling technique was used to select adolescents between the age of 13 and 18 years old and elderly that were at least 60 years of age as at the time of the study. In

each of the selected ward, thirty-two (32) respondents (adolescents and elders) were selected. The sample size of the study was one hundred and ninety-two (192).

Research Instrument for Data Collection

The research instrument used for the study was a fixed response structured and well validated questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of five sections. The first section (Section A) consisted of the personal data of the respondents, section B consisted of fixed response items on indigenous and contemporary foods available for consumption, section C consisted of fixed response items on the perception on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods, section D consisted of fixed response items on the reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods while section E consisted of fixed response items on the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods.

Analysis of Data

The following data analyses were used for the study.

i. Frequency and percentage:

The frequency of respondents' response for each item were counted and the percentages were calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Frequency}}{\text{total number respondents}} \times 100$$

ii. Mean (\bar{x}): The mean of the questionnaire items was interpreted based on the statistical real limits of the numbers as follows;

Response Category	Boundary	Point	Limit
Strongly agree (SA)		4	3.50-4.00
Agree (A)		3	2.50-3.49
Disagree (D)		2	1.50-2.49
Strongly disagree (SD)		1	0.50-1.49

A cut-off point (C) was used to determine accepted or rejected items. The cut-off point was obtained by adding up all the items. The formula for attaining the cut-off point is totaling the nominal values divided by the number of nominal values. That is,

$$COP = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$$

Decision Rule: Any mean between 2.50 and above was considered as agreed, while any mean below 2.50 was considered as disagreed.

iii. **T-test:** The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The t-test was estimated using Statistical Package for Social Science 20 (SPSS 20).

Results

Research Question 1: What are the indigenous and contemporary foods consumed by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State?

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Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of adolescents' and elders' responses to consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods

S/N	Indigenous	Adolescents (N=95) F(5)	Elders (N=97) F(5)	Contemporary	Adolescents (N=95) F(5)	Elders (N=97) F(5)
1.	Èsùrù	27(28.4)	97(100.)	Rice	91(95.8)	69(71.1)
2.	Arùrù	17(17.9)	77(79.4)	Beans products	80(84.2)	84(86.6)
3.	Àbàrí	18(19.0)	87(89.7)	Spaghetti	93(97.9)	17(17.5)
4.	Iyán	69(72.6)	93(95.9)	Noodles	93(97.9)	12(12.3)
5.	Kókò	49(51.6)	95(97.9)	Yam products	93(97.9)	26(26.8)
6.	Sèsé	18(19.0)	87(89.7)	Salad	87(91.6)	15(15.5)
7.	Ègbo	12(12.63)	79(81.4)	Flour products	89(93.7)	18(18.6)
8.	Àádùn	47(49.5)	83(85.6)	Cassava products	81(85.3)	17(17.5)
9.	Òjòjò	16.(16.8)	91(93.8)	Snacks	89(93.7)	28(28.9)
10.	Egidi	29(30.5)	95(97.9)	Potato	69(72.6)	29(29.9)
11.	Èkuru	45(47.3)	91(93.8)	Macaroni	91(95.8)	24(24.7)
12.	Àkàrá Ágbádo	24(25.3)	85(87.6)	Plantain products	89(93.7)	52(53.6)

Key: N= number of respondents, F=frequewncy, % = percent

Table 1 revealed the consumption of some indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in the area of study. The table revealed that more elders consumed èsùrù (100%), arùrù (79.4%), àbàrí (89.7%), iyán (95.9%), kókò (97.9%), sèsé (89.7%), Ègbo (81.4%), Àádùn (85.6%), Òjòjò (93.8%), Egidi (97.9%), Èkuru (93.8%), Àkàrá Ágbádo (87.6%) when compared to adolescents. Only (28.4%) of the adolescents consumed èsùrù, arùrù (17.9%), àbàrí (19.0%), iyán (72.6%), kókò (51.6%), sèsé (19.0%), ègbo (12.63%), àádùn (49.5%), òjòjò (16.8%), egidi (30.5%), èkuru (47.3%), àkàrá ágbádo (25.3%). Similarly, more adolescents consumed rice (95.8%), spaghetti (97.9%), noodles (97.9%), yam products (97.9%), salad (91.6%), flour products (93.7%), cassava products (85.3%), snacks (93.7%), potato (72.6%), macaroni (95.8%), plantain products (93.7%). In essence, elders consumed indigenous food more than adolescents while adolescents consumed contemporary foods more than elders.

Research Question 2: What is the perception of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State?

Table 2: Mean responses of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods

S/N	Perception on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods	N ₁ = 192,	N ₂ = 97,	N ₁ = 95,	C = 2.5
		X ₁	SD	X ₂	X ₂
1.	Indigenous food does not play significant role in human lives like contemporary foods.	2.54*	1.278	3.51*	1.59
2.	Contemporary foods are not acceptable in the society when compared with indigenous foods	2.54	1.139	1.79	3.10*
3.	Contemporary foods are more classy in vogue when compared with indigenous food.	3.04*	1.090	3.62*	2.46
4.	Indigenous foods are not good sources of pleasure, comfort and security like contemporary foods	2.94*	1.209	3.71*	2.19
5.	Indigenous foods offer varieties of dishes and flavour to food most especially in social events.	2.68*	1.116	1.94	3.40*
6.	Indigenous foods take time to prepare when compared with contemporary foods	2.82*	1.249	3.63*	2.03
7.	Indigenous foods disturb the stomach and at times act as laxatives.	2.59*	1.258	3.43*	1.77
8.	Contemporary foods are not fast and easy to prepare.	2.42	1.168	1.97	2.86*
9.	Indigenous foods require multiple cooking methods (frying, steaming, boiling, simmering)	2.91	1.192	3.46*	2.237
10.	Indigenous foods are not symbols of hospitality, social status, and religious significance.	2.83*	1.182	3.45*	2.23

* mean greater than cut-off point (2.5) accepted as agreed.

Key: N₁ -- total number of respondents, N₂ -- number of elders, N₁ -- number of adolescents, C -- cut-off point,

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The table 2 revealed that the mean response of adolescents and elders on items 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9 and 10, ranged from 2.54 to 3.04 which were greater than the cut-off point (2.5). Hence, respondents agreed that indigenous food does not play significant role in human lives like contemporary foods, contemporary foods are classier and in vogue when compared with indigenous foods and that indigenous foods are not good sources of pleasure, comfort and security like contemporary foods. Similarly, respondents agreed that indigenous foods offer varieties of dishes and flavour to food most especially in social events, take time to prepare when compared with contemporary foods, disturb the stomach and at times act as laxatives. Indigenous foods require multiple cooking methods like frying, steaming, boiling and simmering, and that they are not symbols of hospitality, social status, and religious significance. Also, the mean responses of respondents on items 2 (2.45) and 8 (2.42) were lesser than the cut-off point (2.5), hence, the respondents disagreed that contemporary foods are not acceptable in the society when compared with indigenous foods and that contemporary foods are not fast and easy to prepare.

Furthermore, the responses of the adolescents on items 1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9 and 10 were greater than that of the elders. The mean responses of elders on items 2, 5 and 8 were greater than that of adolescents.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the perception of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State.

Table 3: t-test statistics showing the difference in the perception of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods

Variable	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Adolescents	95	30.51	3.984	190	10.577	0.009	Significant
Elders	97	24.00	4.516				

Key: N = number of respondents, X = mean, SD = standard deviation, df=degree of freedom, t-cal=test calculated value

Table 3 revealed that the calculated t-value was 10.577 and the p-value (0.009) was lesser than 0.05 which indicated a significant difference. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the perception of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State is rejected. The table revealed that adolescents had greater mean score (30.51) than elders (24.00) showing that the perception on indigenous and contemporary foods was dependent on age.

Research Question 3: What are the reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State?

Table 4: Mean responses of adolescents and elders on reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods

S/N	Perception on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods	N ₂ =97		N ₁ =95		C=2.5
		X ₂	SD	X ₁	X ₂	
1.	Food production focusing on commodities that have commercial value should shift to promoting the consumption of indigenous foods	2.68*	1.245	1.93	3.41*	
2.	Indigenous foods are not as nutritious as contemporary foods.	2.68*	1.290	3.53*	1.86	
3.	Knowledge in traditional food gathering, preparation and consumption help to create a wealth of unique cultural knowledge and identities among tribes and individuals	3.19*	1.081	3.25*	3.12*	
4.	In addition to their use as foods some foods have medicinal properties.	2.68*	1.294	1.79	3.55*	
5.	Consumption of indigenous foods does not show the value people on their foods	2.69*	1.222	3.47*	1.92	

* mean greater than cut-off point (2.5) accepted as agreed.

Key: N₂ – total number of respondents, N₂ –number of elders, N₁ –number of adolescents, C – cut-off point, X₂-mean response of all respondents, X₁-mean response of elders, X₁-mean response of adolescents, SD-Standard deviation.

Table 4 revealed that the responses of all respondents on all items ranged from 2.68 to 3.19 which were greater than the cut-off point (2.5). Hence, respondents agreed that food production focusing on commodities that have commercial value should shift to promoting the consumption of indigenous food sources, they are not as nutritious as contemporary foods and knowledge in traditional food gathering, preparation, preservation and consumption help to create a wealth of unique cultural knowledge and identities among tribes and individuals. In the same manner, respondents agreed that in addition to their use as foods some indigenous foods have medicinal properties and that their consumption does not show the value people place on their foods. Furthermore, the mean responses of adolescents on items 2, 3 and 5 were greater than that of elders while the mean responses of elders on items 1 and 4 were greater than that of adolescents.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State

Table 5: t-test statistics showing the difference in the perception of adolescents and elders on reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods

Variable	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Adolescents	95	13.97	2.248	190	0.396	0.425	Not significant
Elders	97	13.86	1.658				

Key: N = number of respondents, \bar{X} =mean, Sd=satndard deviation, df=degree of freedom, t-cal =t-test calculated value

Table 5 revealed that the calculated t-value was 0.396 and the p-value (0.425) was greater than 0.05 which indicated a non-significant difference. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State was accepted.

Research Question 4: What is the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State?

Table 6: Mean responses of adolescents and elders on frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods

S/N	Indigenous Foods	\bar{X}_1	SD	\bar{X}_2	\bar{X}_3	Contemporary Foods	$N_1 = 192$		$N_2 = 97$		$N_3 = 95$	
							\bar{X}_1	SD	\bar{X}_1	SD	\bar{X}_1	SD
1.	<i>Èsùrù</i>	1.73 [#]	0.831	1.48 [*]	1.97 [#]	Rice	2.57 [^]	0.565	2.89 [^]	2.26 [#]		
2.	<i>Arùrù</i>	1.41 [*]	0.492	1.32 [*]	1.49 [*]	Beans and products	2.73 [^]	0.509	2.63 [^]	2.84 [^]		
3.	<i>Àbàrí</i>	2.08 [#]	0.849	1.37 [*]	2.77 [^]	Spaghetti	2.11 [#]	0.942	2.89 [^]	1.35 [*]		
4.	<i>Iyán</i>	2.45 [#]	0.707	1.91 [#]	2.98 [^]	Noodles	2.09 [#]	0.955	2.92 [^]	1.29 [*]		
5.	<i>Kókò</i>	2.26 [#]	0.802	1.57 [#]	2.94 [^]	Yam products	2.08 [#]	0.917	2.76 [^]	1.42 [*]		
6.	<i>Sèsé</i>	2.01 [#]	0.912	1.19 [*]	2.80 [^]	Salad	2.07 [#]	0.869	2.73 [^]	1.42 [*]		
7.	<i>Ègbo</i>	1.92 [#]	0.882	1.19 [*]	2.63 [^]	Flour products	2.08 [#]	0.929	2.81 [^]	1.37 [*]		
8.	<i>Àádùn</i>	2.22 [#]	0.853	1.51 [#]	2.92 [^]	Cassava products	2.08 [#]	0.765	2.54 [^]	1.63 [#]		
9.	<i>Òjòjò</i>	2.02 [#]	0.895	1.21 [*]	2.80 [^]	Snacks	2.13 [#]	0.932	2.85 [^]	1.42 [*]		
10.	<i>Egidi</i>	2.24 [#]	0.815	1.62 [#]	2.85 [^]	Potatto	2.09 [#]	0.811	2.56 [^]	1.63 [#]		
11.	<i>Èkuru</i>	2.32 [#]	0.798	1.71 [#]	2.92 [^]	Macaroni	2.25 [#]	0.910	2.92 [^]	1.60 [#]		
12.	<i>Ákárá</i>	2.10 [#]	0.844	1.44 [*]	2.75 [^]	Plantain products	2.41 [#]	0.800	2.78 [^]	2.04 [#]		
	<i>Àgbádo</i>											

* – never, # – seldom, ^ – Frequently

Key: N_1 – total number of respondents, N_2 – number of elders, N_3 – number of adolescents, \bar{X}_1 – mean response of all respondents, \bar{X}_2 – mean response of elders, \bar{X}_3 – mean response of adolescents, SD – Standard deviation

Table 6 presents the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders. The table revealed that *èsùrù*, *arùrù*, *àbàrí*, *sèsé*, *ègbo*, *òjòjò* and *ákárá àgbádo* were never consumed by most adolescents. Other indigenous foods such as *iyán*, *kókò*, *àádùn*, *egidi* and *èkuru* were seldom consumed by adolescents. Elders consumed *àbàrí*, *iyán*, *kókò*, *sèsé*, *ègbo*, *àádùn*, *òjòjò*, *egidi*, *èkuru* and *ákárá àgbádo* frequently. In terms of contemporary foods, elders consumed only very few contemporary (rice, cassava products, potato and macaroni) seldom. Majority of the elders never consumed spaghetti, noodles, yam products, salad, flour

products and snacks. Adolescents frequently consumed rice, beans and beans products, spaghetti, noodles, yam and yam products, salad, flour products, cassava products, snacks, potato, macaroni and plantain products.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State.

Table 7: t-test statistics showing the difference in the perception of adolescents and elders on reasons for consuming indigenous and contemporary foods

Variable	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Adolescents	95	50.78	4.921	190	-1.782	0.019	Significant
Elders	97	50.09	5.286				

Key: N = number of respondents, \bar{X} = mean, Sd = standard deviation, df = degree of freedom, t-cal = t-test calculated value

Table 7 revealed that the calculated t-value was -1.782 and the p-value (0.019) was greater than 0.05 which indicated a significant difference. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the frequency of consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods by adolescents and elders in ANWLGA, Ondo State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Indigenous foods are native to a particular area. Some of the indigenous foods that were observed to be consumed by the elders in Akoko North-West Local Government Area of Ondo State included *èsúrú, arùrù, àbàrí, iyán, kókò, sèsé, ègbo, àádùn, òjòjò, egidi, èkuru and ákára ágbádo*. Only *iyán, kókò*, and *àádùn* were consumed by more than half of the adolescents sampled. The reverse was however the case for contemporary foods. More adolescents were interested in contemporary foods than the elders. These contemporary foods include rice, spaghetti, noodles, yam and products, salad, flour products,

cassava products, snacks, potato, macaroni and plantain and products. Earlier studies by Fasakin (2018) have reported that in terms of the frequency of consumption, some indigenous foods such as *ikete*, *àmúyagi*, *tapon* and *letti* were occasionally consumed, *èpúpá/èkúkùyùn*, *ckuu ogede* and *am'yale* were never consumed while *gbanunu* was consumed frequently. The general shift in occupation and massive neglect of farming has led to the importation of food items such as rice and wheat which in turn has changed consumption pattern (Workman, 2018).

Elders in the study must have developed the habit of consuming indigenous foods at a tender age. Similarly, the observed high consumption of contemporary foods among adolescents could be as a result of “get food fast” syndrome common in this generation. Adolescents have been observed to have a high appetite for fast and junk foods (Adeniyi, 2005). Most of the indigenous foods in the study takes a lot of time to cook. For instance, *èsúrú* which is a particular type of yam is boiled under high temperature for a number of hours to get cooked for consumption.

In addition, the study examined the perception of adolescents and elders on the consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State. It was observed that there was a variation in the perception of adolescents and elders on consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods in ANWLGA, Ondo State. Elders in the study had good attitude to indigenous foods. Adolescents perceived that indigenous food does play significant roles in human lives like contemporary foods, hence, they were not acceptable in the society when compared with indigenous foods. They also believed that contemporary foods are classier and in vogue when compared with indigenous foods and felt that indigenous foods were not good sources of pleasure, comfort and security like contemporary foods. Adolescents also wrongly perceived

that indigenous foods do not offer varieties of dishes and flavour to food most especially in social events, they take time to prepare when compared with contemporary foods, disturb the stomach and at times act as laxatives and require multiple cooking methods (frying, steaming, boiling, simmering). Despite the significance of indigenous foods in hospitality, social status and religion, adolescents perceived that indigenous foods were not symbols of hospitality, social status, and religious significance. Earlier studies on indigenous foods are not really age centred, however, some of the few available have reported similar findings. Fasakin (2018) reported that indigenous foods in Ondo town were consumed by elders in the area. Also, Adefalu and Fawole (2014) noted that teenagers perceived that indigenous food takes longer time to cook, poorly packaged, have cultural affiliation, does not appeal to eyes and were not readily available, hence, they hardly consume the indigenous foods.

There are several reasons for the attitude of adolescents and elders to the consumption of indigenous and contemporary foods. Some of these reasons are commercial value of food items, perceived nutritional value of indigenous foods by adolescents, knowledge on traditional food gathering, preparation, preservation, consumption and the cultural value. Similar findings were reported by Adefalu and Fawole (2014). They reported that there is a gradual decline in the consumption of indigenous foods among the Nigerian teenagers. This was due to the fact that the foods were sold by vendors who hardly maintained good hygiene and rarely cooked at homes and restaurants.

Conclusion

Indigenous foods are perceived by adolescents to be insignificant in human lives since they are thought of as not good sources of pleasure, comfort and security like the

contemporary foods. Adolescents also believed that indigenous foods have no relationship with culture, social status and religion. However, indigenous foods offer varieties of dishes and flavour to food most especially in social events and take time to prepare when compared with contemporary foods. Elders on the other hand had a broader knowledge and understanding on the nutritional, economic, cultural and religious features of indigenous foods. Knowledge about indigenous foods are not adequately passed down to the younger generation by the elders as most adolescents were unaware of the nutritional, cultural and economic benefits of indigenous foods. This poor knowledge was also exhibited in their frequency of consumption of indigenous foods. Only very few adolescents consumed indigenous food in Akoko North-West Local Government Area of Ondo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

- the indigenous foods, most especially the ones that are not often consumed by adolescents should be encouraged through traditional kitchens, television broadcast, publication of recipes in magazines and dailies;
- education, promotion and social marketing to expose the importance of indigenous foods to adolescents. This can be targeted to key age groups such as children, adolescents and youths;
- nutrition education programmes to address challenges related to promoting or enhancing consumption of a varied diet including indigenous foods or foods offering wide variety should be organised by educational institutions and the government; and

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- strategic partnerships and multi-sectoral linkages (government level) need to be established to support and advocate the importance of traditional foods on a wider basis and to share experiences most especially with adolescents.

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